

ISic0846

Epitaph for Euphrosyne

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Εὐφροσύνη ·
2. · χρηστή ·
3. καὶ · ἄμεμπτος ·
4. ἔζησε · ἔτη · μ ·

Apparatus

Text based upon photograph

Translation (en)

Euphrosyne, worthy and blameless, has lived for 40 years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492474

EDCS 39102000

PHI 140323

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0029 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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